

Demographic and Ethnic Changes, Creating Challenges for Society: A Sociological Analysis of Karachi during 2014 - 2015.

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Abstract:

This study is related to Karachi, one of the largest urban settlement of the world and most populated and largest city and economic hub of Pakistan. Demographically this is the heterogeneous city with different types of ethnic, sub-ethnic, religious, and sectarian groups, even mix ethnic and sectarian groups with a verity of characteristics. In current situation population of Karachi is under depression and uncertainty. Demographic situations are changing rapidly; the population of the city is developing ethnic pockets. The city Karachi has its different dimensions depends upon, political chapters, economic problems, ethnic pressures, prominent signs of international interventions and conflicts.

Specific objectives of the study were, to find out current demographic changes in the population of Karachi and its impact on the changing patterns of ethnicity, To find out relationship between changing ethnic pattern and its impacts and challenges created for society, and To find out relationship between changing ethnic patterns, Migrations and current law and order situation of the city. The study is exploratory in nature, and research was initiated through personal and professional dialogue with stakeholders, to evaluate the problems through previous studies, Focus Group Discussions of basic stakeholders.

The study was, provide authentic recommendations to solve the demographic, changes especially due to migrations and ethnic problems; it helps the policymakers for proper planning of the city. As well as this study will be an asset to my institution and helpful for a future researcher.

Keywords: *Heterogeneous, Ethnic, Demographic, population patterns, Sectarian, Extremism.*

Introduction:

Karachi is not only the largest metropolis of Pakistan and its commercial hub, it is also known As a 'mini-Pakistan' (Budhani, et, al 2010) it is one of the largest urban settlement of the world and most populated and largest city of Pakistan. Demographically this is the heterogeneous city with different types of ethnic groups, sub-ethnic group, religious groups, sectarian groups, even mix ethnic and sectarian groups with verity of characteristics, if we will example of one ethnic group "Muhajir" those are Migrated from India during independence of Pakistan, this group is again divided into different groups based on origin of their relationships from Indian cities, areas or even languages. Moreover, these subgroups are again divided into an ethnic group based on a relationship with different religious sects.

In current situation population of Karachi is under depression and uncertainty. The city is developing ethnic pockets to live in various areas. Most of the peoples prefer to live in an area where the population of their ethnicity is living or dominant. Karachi is the capital city of Sindh province and Sindh was not homogenous area before partition and there are no or rare examples of grouping or conflicts.

In Pakistan ethnicity impacts at large, peoples are known with reference to their languages, territorial origin or affiliations with religious groups. Since the independence of Pakistan five major ethnic groups are dominated by system, Punjabi as largest and dominant ethnic group in Punjab and also in Karachi, Pathan (Pashtun) ethnic group is spread all over the country, most dominant in Khyber Pakhtoon Kiawah, Karachi, and Quetta, Sindhi mostly limited to Sindh, Baloch in Baluchistan and in Karachi, and Muhajir's are dominant ethnic group Karachi. In this way it is easy to understand that Karachi is the city in which several ethnic groups are living, Punjabis, Sindhis, Kashmiris, Seraikis, Pakhtuns, Balochis, Memons, Bohras, Muhajrs, Ismailis, and Afghan refugees.

The city Karachi has its different dimensions depends upon, political chapters, economic problems, ethnic pressures, prominent signs of international interventions and conflicts. It is also a violent city, probably the most violent city of comparable size in South Asia. (Abbas, Azmat. 2001).

Within years of history, we can find various eras of city related to demographic and violent situations. Sectarian groups and their role, emerging of MQM, and pressure of ethnic groups from Balochi, Pakhtun, Sindhi, Punjabi etc, between 1994 and 2006, extremist Sunni militants waged a campaign of bomb attacks and assassinations against the city's Shia minority (Abbas 2001). Mean Karachi city is experiencing rapid changes in demographic stability and situation is becoming dangerous.

In current situation ethnicity is rising rapidly, the groups which were dominant from years are going to recessive or in defending a position, different areas of the city are divided into different ethnic groups even person related to one ethnic group cannot move in the other area where another ethnic group is dominant.

The significance of the Study:

This research was focused on causes and impacts of changing demographic situations and to identify the challenges created by growing ethnicity. This study will helpful for policy makers to control the situation, and identify the impacts of ethnicity on new generations and development of youth and humanity. It is the great state of discomfort that ethnicity creates the situation in which cast, languages, and affiliations are dominant over the humanity. In this way, this study will identify the ways to reduce the domination of ethnicity in the city and promote the humanity.

Youth, Professionals, business community, NOG's and public sector will be involved in this study by focus group discussion and through questionnaires, data analysis and results will guide us to evaluate the situation and effective conclusion and recommendations will find out for policymakers, community mobilizers, researchers, and for the betterment of population itself.

Literature Review:

Sociological, Anthropological, Demographical or Population Studies plays an important role in the planning of any largely populated Urban or industrialized city. In past and present situations there are various studies related to urban life of Karachi, in 2000 The Pakistan Development Review has published a study of Javed Ashraf and Birjee Ashraf titled as Ethnicity and Earnings: an analysis of Data for Karachi, in this study the earnings or economic share or productivity by various ethnic groups were analyzed. Ethnic groups Sindhi, Punjabi, Pakhtun, Baloch, and Muhajir were the variables of this study and data from the collected from AERC/KDA, a socio-economic survey of 1987 was analyzed, gender, age and ethnic group wise share of income was evaluated. In conclusion remarks study author said: The results do not support the contention that ethnic background plays a major role in determining earnings in Pakistan.

Another study of online journal of CERISciences Po presented a study by Laurent Gayer 2, with title "Ethnic" and "Religious" conflicts in Karachi Pakistan. The introduction to this study starts from the history of Karachi and analyzed the most prominent events of city related to ethnic and religious situations. This is the complete qualitative study most probably just a part of the history of the Karachi city. This study covers the political situation, demographic situation, status of education, employment, economic situation housing etc. focusing on ethnic issues a part of this study is subtitled as "The New Hong Kong or another Beirut" this study also discussed the objective and activities of different ethnic groups.

Another research studies related to this issue, is Working paper of Crises stated series with title "The open city: Social network and violence in Karachi" this working paper is written by Azmat Ahmed kaker, Hussin Bux Mallah in 2010 this working paper described the situation analysis of Karachi city historically and role of social system its relationship with various social groups, political parties. This paper also describes the social phenomena of the city and discusses that how violence increases and what the major factor which plays role in violence are. A Study of 2012 by Journal of political studies vol.19, issues 1.2012 with the title "Contending Ethnic Identities: an issues to Pakistan's Internal Security, The Case of Karachi" written by Umbreen Javaid and Rehana Saeed Hashmi both are related with Department of Political Science as Chairperson and Director of

Center for South Asian studies, this study is focused on ethnic heterogeneity and problems created by ethnic ideology, defining the ethnic groups, conflicts and ethnic composition of Pakistan as well as Karachi Sindh, study defines some basic elements of ethnic conflicts like ethnic militant and sectarian groups, Demographic pressure, ethnopolitical conflicts, Migrations etc. in conclusion studies emphasized on role of state, failure of government policies, and declared that ethnic conflicts or dangerous for internal security o country.

In 2012 United States Institute of Peace has published a study with title of “Conflicts dynamics in Karachi” written by freelance journalist and columnists for the Pakistani newspaper Dawn Mrs. Huma Yousif, in this statistics are given about killings and conflicts by various groups, impacts of violence and ethnic conflicts on economy and discussed about various militant wings of political parties, according to study the key of stability in Karachi is representative of power sharing and dominancy over city. In conclusion, the study said that the only solution to incessant ethnic political violence and criminal activities are political negotiations leading to a culture of representative politics.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To find out the current demographic changes in the population of Karachi and its impact on the changing patterns of ethnicity.
2. To find out the relationship between changing the ethnic pattern and its impacts on political situations of Karachi.
3. To find out the relationship between changing ethnic patterns and current law and order situation if the city.

Research Questions:

1. What are the impacts of Demographic changes on socio-political situation of Karachi, Pakistan?
2. What should be the role of state and law enforcement agencies to control situations created by demographic changes?

Research Methodology:

As the focus of this research was to unearth demographic and ethnic changes and its impacts of Karachi through sociological observations, research was initiated through personal and professional dialogue with stakeholders, by four Focus Group Discussions, including religious leaders, Sociologists, representatives of Social Welfare Department, NGO representatives etc. and analysis of secondary data from previous literature, Books and periodicals.

Results:

Qualitative Analysis/Group Discussions

Five Focus group discussions were arranged in different Districts of Karachi City, with related stakeholders, i.e NGO representatives who are working on population and peacebuilding issues, police department, district administrations representatives, religious leaders, and community representatives.

The major objectives of these group discussions were to analyze views of different stakeholders on the basis of their experiences and four important questions were discussed.

1. What are demographic changes occurring in Karachi city?
 2. What are ethnic changes occurring in Karachi?
 3. What are relationships between changing population patterns and its impact on socio-political situations of Karachi?
 4. What is a relationship between changing ethnic patterns and current law and order situation in Karachi?
- Participants took interest in threadbare discussion, at some stages probing questions were asked to get better results.

1-What Demographic changes occurring in Karachi:

While discussing on above situation in all four focus group discussions, most of the participants were of the views that continuous population growth in the country, Migrations from different provinces and cities of the country, illegal migrants from Afghanistan, Bangladesh and other countries are major means of demographic changes. Some of the participants were their views that these situations are multiplying the population of Karachi city. During all group discussion, it was observed that majority of stakeholders were agreed that demographic situation of the city is ever changing due to huge migrants peoples coming from different parts of Country, especially from Northern areas and internal areas of Sindh and Baluchistan.

2. What are ethnic changes occurring in Karachi?

While discussing on problems related to ethnicity and changes related ethnic groups participants took active participation and with consensus of them it was revealed that there are some dominant ethnic groups in city and different parts of city are just dedicated to specific type of ethnic groups, i.e. Liyari for Balochs, Johar, Gulshan Hadid, Sachal Goth for Sindh's, Nusrat Clooney for Pathan, Pakhtoons, Majority of city with Muhajors etc.

Moreover, during discussions, it was also revealed that population of Karachi is also divided by various religious groups, sectarian groups, and even sub- sectarian groups.

3-What are relationships between changing population patterns and its impact on socio-political situations in Karachi?

During Focus groups discussion impacts of population changes discussed Interestingly, it revealed that population changes develop major challenges for a citizen of Karachi as well as for administration, policymakers, and all stakeholders. According to discussion situation promoted the highest level of violence in city, drugs, criminal gangs, ethnic conflicts, aggressive behavior rise up. Resultantly thousands of killing occurred in last 10 years. During the discussion, it was also revealed that current situation mismanaged the society and socio-economic conditions are very verse in the city. During the discussion it was disclosed that national and international investment in the city is stopped that can create a huge economic disaster in future, moreover, a large number of industries and investors are moving their assets to Punjab or even to other countries.

4. What is a relationship between changing ethnic patterns and current law and order situation in Karachi?

Discussing on impacts of ethnic changes and challenges in city it was revealed that law and order situation is highly troubled it is assumed that city is divided into different pockets owned by different ethnic groups and there is no or rare control of law enforcement agencies, Karachi being home of all socio-cultural groups living in Pakistan have its own importance but due to powerful ethnic rules and norms becoming challenging city to live. During the discussion, it was revealed that this is not a new situation but it result of more than thirty years interventions and mismanagement in societal norms, values and ethics, and its major cause is rapid demographic changes, migrations, increase in religious extremism and political use of ethnicity in the city. According to the discussion, it was revealed that major portion of society doesn't believe on different channels of law execution authorities in the city and confused about their role to control law and order crises. Gang warfare, target killing, short time kidnapping, suicide bombing, street crime etc. creates psychopathy's among the population of Karachi.

Conclusion:

1. Demographic conditions of Karachi are changing rapidly, which creates administrative challenges in the city.
2. Ethnicity is increasing day by day and ethnic and sub-ethnic groups are creating difficulties for society at large and administration specifically.

3. Rapid ethnic changes develop extremism in a society that is breaking the harmony among citizens.
4. Religious, Sectarian and sub-sectarian groups are emerging rapidly and enhance religious extremism in the city.
5. Karachi is facing internal and external threats and interventions those are playing a major role in promoting ethnic and religious extremism in the city.
6. Demographic and ethnic changes create major disorders in society and socio-economic conditions are becoming very verse.
7. Law and order situation is uncontrolled in the city and demographic and ethnic changes are among major causes.

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